

Effect of sodium chloride on surface and thermodynamic properties of aerosol-OT in aqueous medium

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The surface tension has been measured for bis-(2-ethyl hexyl) sodium sulfosuccinate (A-OT) in water and aqueous NaCl at 298, 303 and 308 K. The values of critical micelle concentration (CMC), maximum surface excess concentration ($\Gamma_{\max}$) and minimum area per molecule ($A_{\min}$) of the surfactant at air-liquid interface have been evaluated. Thermodynamic parameters of micellization as well as adsorption have also been evaluated. The micellization process is exothermic while adsorption is endothermic in nature.

The physico-chemical properties of surfactant solutions in aqueous medium with/without electrolyte are important in understanding the mechanism of these interactions. These studies are of significant importance in the field of interaction of medicine, agrochemicals, detergency, solubilization of organic compounds in aqueous solution, enhanced oil recovery and in metallurgical processes¹⁻⁴. The surface and thermodynamic properties for such systems in the presence/absence of electrolytes provide valuable information regarding the solute-solute and solute-solvent interaction. In the present investigation we report the data for surface properties such as surface excess concentration ($\Gamma_{\max}$), minimum area per molecule at the air-liquid interface ($A_{\min}$), surface pressure at CMC (π_{cmc}), and thermodynamic parameters for micellization/adsorption of bis-(2-ethyl hexyl) sodium sulfosuccinate (A-OT) in aqueous sodium chloride at 298, 303, 308 K.

Results and discussion

The CMC values obtained from the sharp break point in the plots of surface tension versus log [surfactant] are presented in Table 1. The observed value of CMC for pure surfactant at 298 K agrees well with those reported in literature^{5,6}. The CMC have also been evaluated from the viscosity measurements and recorded in parentheses (Table 1). These are in good agreement with those determined from surface tension data. It may be seen from Table 1 that CMC values increase with increase in temperature. In the absence of additives the CMC of ionic surfactants generally increases

Table 1. CMC, surface excess concentration ($\Gamma_{\max}$), minimum area per molecule ($A_{\min}$) and the surface pressure at the CMC (π_{cmc}) for bis-(2-ethyl hexyl) sodium sulfosuccinate (A-OT) in water and aqueous NaCl systems.

[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (K)	CMC $\times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$\Gamma_{\max} \times 10^{10}$ (mol cm ⁻²)	$A_{\min} \times 10^2$ (nm ²)	$\pi_{\text{cmc}} \times 10^3$ (Nm ⁻¹)
0	298	2.48 (2.42)	2.42	68.61	35.37
	303	2.72 (2.80)	2.29	72.50	36.68
	308	3.02 (3.00)	2.16	76.87	38.70
		2.50 ^a			
0.025	298	1.90 (1.92)	1.50	110.69	43.37
	303	2.10 (2.08)	1.39	119.45	44.43
	308	2.22 (2.20)	1.28	129.71	45.64
0.050	298	1.70 (1.72)	1.54	107.81	48.57
	303	1.87 (1.84)	1.33	124.83	49.38
	308	2.04 (2.00)	1.18	140.70	50.47
0.075	298	1.50 (1.48)	1.54	107.81	49.17
	303	1.64 (1.66)	1.30	127.72	50.15
	308	1.86 (1.84)	1.12	148.24	51.18

Values of CMC given in parentheses have been evaluated from viscosity measurements.

^aLiterature value of CMC for pure Aerosol-OT at 298 K (Ref. 5, 6).

with increase in temperature^{7,8}. It follows from Table 1 that CMC of the surfactant decreases in the presence of sodium chloride. The effect of addition of NaCl on the CMC values of A-OT can be explained on the fact that addition of an electrolyte increases the size and alters the charge on the micelles because of which there is increase in diameter of the spheres through uncoiling of the paraffin chains and

results in depression of CMC^{6,9,10}. Corrin *et al.*¹¹ studied the effect of the addition of NaCl to sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and reported an approximate 25% reduction in CMC of SDS. Burcik¹² and Acharya¹³ also reported a decline in the CMC of SDS with the addition of salts. These literature observations are in consistency with the results shown in the present investigation.

Maximum surface excess concentration ($\Gamma_{\max}$) values at the air-liquid interface have been obtained using Gibb's adsorption equation¹⁴,

$$\Gamma_{\max} = -1/2.303 nRT (d\gamma/d \log C)_T \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of particles released per surfactant molecule in the solution, R , the gas constant and $(d\gamma/d \log C)_T$ represents the slope of the surface tension versus $\log C$ plot below the CMC at constant temperature T . In the present investigation $n = 2$ for anionic surfactant. The calculated values for $\Gamma_{\max}$ for the studied systems at three temperature are also presented in Table 1. An examination of Table 1 revealed that $\Gamma_{\max}$ values decrease with increase in temperature. It may be due to enhanced molecular thermal agitational effect at higher temperature. A further decrease in $\Gamma_{\max}$ values in the presence of NaCl may be due to the fact that addition of NaCl causes a displacement of surfactant molecules from the air-liquid interface to the bulk phase.

The minimum area per molecule ($A_{\min}$) at the liquid-air interface have been calculated using the following equation¹⁴,

$$A_{\min} = 10^{14}/N \Gamma_{\max} \quad (2)$$

where N is Avogadro's number, $A_{\min}$ values for the studied systems are given in the Table 1. It may be seen from Table 1 that $A_{\min}$ values increase with increase in temperature as well as with the concentration of NaCl in the surfactant solution. The observed increase in $A_{\min}$ values may be due to ion-dipole interaction of electrolyte ion and the surfactant polar head group which facilitate the micellization of surfactant in the bulk. The behaviour can be explained in terms of enhanced compatibility of surfactant with the solvent in the presence of NaCl, thereby, causing a shift of surfactant molecules from air-liquid interface to the bulk phase.

Surface pressure at the CMC (π_{cmc}) have been calculated using the following equation¹⁴,

$$\pi_{\text{cmc}} = \gamma_0 - \gamma_{\text{cmc}} \quad (3)$$

where γ_0 = surface tension of water and γ_{cmc} = surface tension of surfactant solution at CMC. Surface pressure at the

CMC (π_{cmc}) is an index of effectiveness of a surfactant at CMC. π_{cmc} values are presented in Table 1 which shows a marginal increase with increase in temperature.

Thermodynamic parameters of micellization like ΔG_m^0 , ΔS_m^0 and ΔH_m^0 have been calculated using the eqs.¹⁴ (4), (5) and (6) respectively.

$$\Delta G_m^0 = RT \ln X \quad (4)$$

(where X is CMC of surfactant in terms of mole fraction)

$$\Delta S_m^0 = [-d(\Delta G_m^0)/dT]_p \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H_m^0 = \Delta G_m^0 + T\Delta S_m^0 \quad (6)$$

The thermodynamic parameters of micellization for surfactant in aqueous NaCl have been calculated using eqs. (4–6) and are presented in Table 2. The negative ΔG_m^0 values indicate that the process of micellization is spontaneous. Decrease in ΔG_m^0 values with increase in temperature may be due to the desolvation of the surfactant hydrophilic group at higher temperature¹⁵. A further decrease in ΔG_m^0 values with the addition of NaCl to surfactant solution facilitates the micellization. This can be attributed to the water structure breaking effect of NaCl as well as decreased hydration of the surfactant molecules in the presence of an electrolyte¹⁶.

The ΔH_m^0 values are negative and ΔS_m^0 values are positive. The negative values of ΔH_m^0 and positive values of ΔS_m^0 favours the process of micellization.

Thermodynamic parameters of adsorption like ΔG_{ad}^0 , ΔH_{ad}^0 and ΔS_{ad}^0 have been calculated using the following relations at constant pressure¹⁷.

$$\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0 = \Delta G_m^0 - 6.023 \times 10^{-1} \pi_{\text{cmc}} A_{\min} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S_{\text{ad}}^0 = -d(\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0)/dT \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta H_{\text{ad}}^0 = \Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0 + T\Delta S_{\text{ad}}^0 \quad (9)$$

The values of ΔG_{ad}^0 , ΔH_{ad}^0 and ΔS_{ad}^0 are presented in Table 2. The lower ΔG_{ad}^0 values compared to ΔG_m^0 (Table 2) indicate that adsorption of the surfactant molecules at the air-liquid interface is preferred over the micellization. The ΔS_{ad}^0 values are all positive and larger than ΔS_m^0 . This may be due to more degree of freedom of the surfactant molecules at the air-liquid interface compared to that in the cramped interior of micelle^{18,19}.

The ΔH_{ad}^0 values are positive and this indicates that larger number of H-bonds between paraffin chain and water molecules are broken during the process of adsorption at the air-liquid interface.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of the micellization/adsorption of bis-(2-ethyl hexyl) sodium sulfosuccinate (A-OT) in water and aqueous NaCl systems

[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (K)	$-\Delta G_{m}^0/-\Delta G_{ad}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H_{m}^0/\Delta H_{ad}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S_{m}^0/\Delta S_{ad}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
0	298	24.88/39.50		
	303	25.00/41.10	16.82/66.77	0.027/0.356
	308	25.15/43.06		
0.025	298	25.48/54.39		
	303	25.66/57.62	11.12/160.54	0.046/0.720
	308	25.94/61.59		
0.050	298	25.76/57.30		
	303	25.95/63.07	14.13/289.00	0.039/1.162
	308	26.15/68.92		
0.075	298	26.07/57.99		
	303	26.26/64.84	16.40/362.08	0.032/1.409
	308	26.39/72.08		

Experimental

The anionic surfactant bis-(2-ethyl hexyl) sodium sulfosuccinate (Aerosol-OT or A-OT, purity 98.5%) obtained from S. D. Fine chemicals and A.R. grade sodium chloride (B.D.H., purity 99.9%) were used without further purification. The solutions were prepared in the doubly distilled water having a specific conductance of 2.00×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹ at 298.15 K.

Surface tensions of various solutions were determined by the dropweight method using a specially designed stalagmometer described elsewhere²⁰ at three different temperatures. The stalagmometer was calibrated by determining the surface tension of pure liquids. The measurements were made in a thermostat (Tempstar, model KW 201A) which provided temperature control of ± 0.01 K.

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